

Text and architecture: YBC 5022 and BM 15285 as “manuals of an architect”

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Abstract: In all periods of human history, the profession of an architect demanded a wide range of knowledge and abilities: the inspired vision of the artist and expertise in various materials, proficiency in mathematics and organisational skills. Are there cuneiform texts that can be associated with architects and their professional training? After analysing the list of coefficients YBC 5022 and the famous tablet of geometrical problems BM 15285 against the background of archaeological and pictorial evidence, I can show that these texts served as an “architect’s manual.” It has already been suggested based on textual and mathematical grounds that the origins of Babylonian mathematics go back to the Ur III period. I shall argue that this was also the period when the training of architects in exact science started.

Keywords: Architect, architecture, construction, mathematics, lists of coefficients, geometry, stereometry, education, ornaments.

This paper¹ was presented at RAI 61 within the framework of the workshop “Math and Realia” dedicated to the memory of Aizik A. Vaiman.² Vaiman wrote about the use of Sumero-Babylonian mathematics in architecture:

By and large, the applied mathematics of Sumerians and Babylonians was rather the mathematics of “bookkeepers” and “economists” than of “technicians” and “engineers.” The number of man-days required for construction work, the amount of food needed for workers and the construction materials to be supplied, etc. were calculated for a building project. There is no data about any technical computations by ancient builders of quantities characterizing the stability of a construction, the strength of its balks, and so forth.³

1 Due to the limitation in length of RAI 61 contributions, many statements and suggestions are only tackled or mentioned in passing in the present article and will be fully developed elsewhere. BT – siglum of texts excavated in the British excavations of Balawat (Imgur-Ilil), see Parker 1963. I am most grateful to M.E.J. Richardson for immensely improving my English. The remaining mistakes are all mine.

2 http://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=vaiman_a_a. (last access 28.08.2016).

3 Vaiman 1961: 207: “В целом прикладная математика шумеров и вавилонян была скорее математикой «бухгалтеров» и «экономистов», чем «техников» и «инженеров». Так, при постройке какого-либо сооружения рассчитывалось количество человеко-дней, необходимое для проведения работ, продуктов питания для содержания рабочих, строительных материалов и т. д. Нет данных, которые свидетельствовали бы о том, что древние строители занимались техническими расчетами для определения величин, характеризующих устойчивость здания, крепость его перекрытий и т. п.” Here and below the quotations from Vaiman’s works were

This is also assumed to have been expected of a Mesopotamian architect in the present contribution. The architect would have been the organizer of a construction project and the designer of a building, including its general concept, decor and minor details. Mastery of the technical aspects of construction derived from age-accumulated know-how, which was sometimes quite sophisticated.⁴ The principles of mechanics and statics were also a matter of empirical knowledge and experience, not of theoretically based computations.

An architect belongs to one of the most ancient professions, and I shall argue that it was not just one of the oldest, but also one for which specialised occupational training has been supplied from earliest times. In Mesopotamia the word *šidim* “builder” is attested as early as Uruk IV and III periods.⁵ In Sumerian it existed on its own and in collocations: *šidim-ḪAR*, “grinder constructor;” *šidim-abzu*, probably “builder, irrigator;” *nu-banda₃ šidim* and *ugula šidim*, “overseer and foreman of master-builders;” *gal-šidim* or *šidim-gal*, “chief builder.”⁶ There is a remarkable abundance of expressions designating specific qualifications and ranks of specialist builders even in the early periods. An inscribed Old Akkadian architect’s seal testifies to

translated into English by the present author and edited by M. Ossendrijver.

4 See, e.g., Weidner 1954: 146; Freydanck 1985: 343.

5 Neumann 1996: 156 with n. 20 and 162 with n. 76.

6 Neumann 1996: 162. The single attestation of *muš-da-ma* applied to humans in Gudea Cylinder B (RIME E3/1.1.7 Cyl.B iii 16) is, apparently, a mark of high literary style. The person working as a *dub-sar šidim*, “builder’s scribe,” is known from the pre-Sargonic and Neo-Sumerian periods.

the high status of its owner and the responsibilities with which he was entrusted.⁷ By the time of Hammurabi the architect's trade was so well established that six paragraphs of the Code concern legal issues which may arise in conjunction with architect's professional risks and honorary.⁸

Akkadian developed an amazingly vast variety of expressions for an architect. The two most common terms, *itinnu* (^{lu}ŠITIM) and *šitimgallu* (^{lu}ŠITIM.GAL),⁹ derive from the Sumerian *šidim* or *dim*₂. The latter word means "to create,"¹⁰ in lexical lists and bilingual texts it is equated to Akkadian *banû* "to build" and "*epēšu*" "to do, make,"¹¹ interchangeable verbs often occurring in the context of construction (fig. 1).¹² Although the word *šitimgallu* is rarely attested in the common language of the Old Babylonian period,¹³ it assumes a grandiloquent nuance in Standard Babylonian in the Neo-Assyrian royal inscriptions of Sargonids and in the building rituals of the first millennium Assyria and Babylonia.¹⁴

7 For the image, see Boehmer 1965: pl. 28 no. 326; for the inscription Edzard 1968–1969: 15.

8 §§228–233 = xlii 56–xlili 3. See Kitchen/Lawrence 2012: 166–167.

9 Borger 2010: 399, no. 686; CAD I/J 296–297 s.v. *itinnu*, especially lexical section and discussion.

10 ETCSL <http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/edition2/etcsllemma.php?sortbylemma=lemma&letter=d> (last access 28.08.2016). PSD <http://psd.museum.upenn.edu/psd/nepsd-frame.html> (last access 28.08.2016).

11 CAD E 192–193 (lexical section) and 197–200 s.v. *epēšu* 2b and CAD B 84 s.v. *banû*, lexical section.

12 The terms most common in each period are highlighted.

13 An architect (written *šidim-gal* without the determinative) appears as a witness in PBS 8/2 151 (= CBS 7135): 20 (Samsu-iluna 5, receipt for money and sheep), and in PBS 264 (= CBS 7742): 42 (Rim-Sin, year 7 of Isin, legal decision concerning a priestly office; on a tablet which is chipped and *gal* is missing).

In Mari (RA 65, 54 = A. 3562), 19 *šitimgallū* (^{lu}ŠITIM.GAL; xii 54), 31 ^{lu}ŠITIM (xii 68) and 11 apprentices (xii 66) are listed among 955 slaves designated for royal gardens (xii 58–62). This list demonstrates that architects were valuable experts standing out among other slaves. It has an interesting parallel in the NA list of Babylonian deportees, where whole families of architects and chief-architects appear together with a cup-bearer, an engraver and his sister, an architect's wife and a scribe (SAA 7, 154). In the NA list not only professions, patronymics, and family members of professionals are recorded, but the locations of their houses are also indicated.

14 It often appears as an epithet of the god of construction ^dMušda(ma) and the brick god Kulla: Falkenstein 1949: 28; Ambos 2004: 146–147, II.B.2 (= K 4167): 7; pp. 148–149, II.B.2 (= K. 4167): 19, 21; pp. 152–153, II.C.1a (= K 3472): 7; pp. 222–223, II.F.: 35"; for NA royal inscriptions, see Fuchs 1994: 41, Zyl 60 and Clay 1915: 52, 54 = YOS 1 no. 38 ii: 1 (Sargon); RINAP 3/1, 22 vi 57 (Sennacherib); RINAP 4, 104: 35 (Esarhaddon). In all these examples *šitimgallu* is written ideographically. CAD Š/3 129b s.v. *šitimgallu* b quotes VS 3, 93 (= VAT 3106): 18, 21 as an example of the usage of *šitimgallu* as a NB family name. That text should be collated since the reading ^{lu}ŠITIM.GAL as the family name of two individuals is highly improbable. It is a receipt for rental income from a date grove, but *šitimgallu* is not attested in the NB period, with the exception in Nabopolassar's inscription (Da Riva 2013: 83; C 31, 1 ii 21 = 2 ii 26 [= VAB 62 ii 28]), which clearly emulates NA royal rhetoric. Moreover, the word is not found elsewhere as a family name in any period. I note the use of other expressions borrowed from NA royal inscriptions in this cylinder of Nabopolassar, such as DUMU^{mes} UM.ME.A *e-em-qu₂-tim* (ibid.; C 31, 1 ii 17 = 2 ii 22 = [VAB 4, 62 ii 24]) and *talimu* in the next column (Da Riva

The term *itinnu* appears for the first time once as early as in Old Akkadian.¹⁵ In Old Babylonian it is the most common word for an architect and from then on it is found in every dialect of Akkadian. In the Middle Babylonian period *itinnu* already occurs as a family name¹⁶ and in Neo- and Late Babylonian it becomes wide-spread¹⁷ occupational family name of scribes in Sippar, Borsippa, Babylon and Uruk.¹⁸ However, in first millennium Babylonia *itinnu* is only rarely used to designate a builder, being replaced by *arad ekalli*.¹⁹ In Neo-Assyrian *šal(l)ippāiu/šeleppāiu* is used to denote an architect. That word conversely derives from a personal name, corrupted from Šallim-pî-Ea, the construction leader and the "father" of 64 "sons."²⁰

In all periods of human history being an architect has demanded a wide range of knowledge and abilities: the inspired vision of an artist and an expertise in working with various materials, an advanced knowledge of mathematics and mechanical engineering principles, as well as a capacity for skilled organisation. Ancient Mesopotamia demanded the same. The abundance of terminology for specialised builders points to refinements of skill, which in turn led to a hierarchy within the profession. A builder was certainly highly skilled, someone who needed special training including ele-

2013: 85; C 31, 1 iii 15 = 2 iii 6 [= VAB 4 iii 7]; see the discussion in May 2011–2012: 162, n. 31; 163 and below with fns. 27 and 47). I am most grateful to C. Wunsch for sharing her yet unpublished edition of VS 3, 93 and discussing this text with me. For *šitimmaḥḥu*, see MA canonical lu₂ = ša, MSL 12, 131: 79 (= VAT 9717 [copy B]) 79) and Pedersen 1986: 21 (N1 [33]) for further bibliography.

15 See Gelb 1955: 296, no. 40: 16.

16 Brinkman 2006: 28; for *banû* and *itinnu* in MB, see Sassmannhausen 2001: 92.

17 Nielsen 2011: 66.

18 Idem: 69–70 with n. 212, 77 with n. 241, 131, 141, 179 with n. 87, 187–188 with n. 34; Jursa 2005: 217–218, no. 18: 1–2, 4; Kümmel 1979: 35–36. In this connection, note also the Neo-Babylonian family group Rab-banê (Nielsen 2011: 59).

19 Kümmel 1979: 35, 37. *Warad ekalli* (IR₃ E₂.GAL) is once attested in the Old Babylonian period in apposition to ŠITIM in a letter from Awil-Ninurta to Šamaš-ḥasir. That letter concerns Lipit-Ištar, an architect from the town Bīt-asar (or Ea-šar), who is to receive rations of grain and wool from the palace. But according to the king's order he is allotted a field in his town (Hammurabi 31+; TCL 7, 54: 4 = Kraus 1968: 36–37). In Neo-Assyrian *urad ekalli* did not mean an architect, since individuals designated as *urad ekalli* often have other professions (Baker 2017: 218–219).

Note the Hebrew אדריכל derived from Akkadian *arad ekalli*. Interestingly, the same metathesis in the transition of Akkadian *arad* into Hebrew took place in the name of Arad/Urdu-Mullissu, the son and murderer of Sennacherib (Radner 2011: 1407–1408, s.v. Urdu-Mullissu 1), becoming Biblical אֲדָרְמֶלֶךְ (2 Kings 19: 37 = Isaiah 37: 38). Berossus also has metathesis for the name of Urdu-Mullissu (Adramelos *apud* Abydenus 5b [Burstein 1978: 25], see discussion in Parpola 1980: 174). Thus the Aramaic *'ardiklā* is also derived from *arad ekalli* despite H. Kümmel's hesitations (Kümmel 1979: 37, n. 1). For Ahiqar as a *'rdkl' ḥkym*?, "wise builder" (cf. below pp. 258–259 with fns. 24–27), see Moore 2017: 85 with fn. 282. I am grateful to J. Moore for making his yet unpublished dissertation available to me.

20 Apparently he was the chief builder of Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta; see Freydank 1985: 362, VS 21, 17 = MARV 11, 17: 25 and Jakob 2003: 461.

Terms for an architect in Akkadian

Derived from	Oakk	OB	SB	MB	MA	NA	NB
$dim_2 = banû,$ $epēšu$	<i>itinnu</i> only once attested syllabically	<i>itinnu</i> (^{lu2} DIM ₂ / ^{lu2} ŠITIM)	<i>itinnu</i>	^{lu2} ŠITIM (<i>itinnu</i>) Only once attested as a family name	^{lu2} ŠITIM (<i>etinnu</i>)	^{lu2} (gal.)tin foreman of construction as well as canal digging <i>e-tin'</i> (SAAB 5, 25 r. 4-5 ^{lu2} <i>e-tin-na-te</i> (SAA 1, 138: 13)	<i>itinnu</i> very common family name; rarely designates profession
šidim-gal	—	šitimgallu (^{lu2} ŠITIM.GAL)	šitimgallu always but once written ^{lu2} ŠITIM.GAL	—	—	—	See fn. 14
	—	ŠITIM warad ekalli (single attestation, see fn. 19)	—	—	—	—	<i>arad ekalli</i>
<i>mār</i> Šallim-pî-Ea (PN)	—	—	—	—	šal(l)ippāiû/ šal(l)ippāiû/ š/elippāiû	šal(l)ippāiû/ šelepāiû	—

Fig. 1: Terms for an architect in Akkadian.

Fig. 2: Room XXII (XX), South-West Palace, Ninive (Sennacherib). Plans and elevations combined in the depictions of fortifications and landscape (after Barnett/Bleibteu/Turner 1998: pl. 226. © Trustees of the British Museum).

ments of the scribal art. Architects, priests and scribes are often listed together in texts from various periods.²¹

21 In the Neo-Assyrian lists of professionals in the palace staff, six architects and six scribes are grouped together (SAA 7, 13). In the Neo-Assyrian texts temple staff and scribes often appear together with architects. On a slave purchase document of the palace scribe Nabû-tuklatū'a, two architects are followed by two scribes in the list of witnesses (790 BCE; Deller/Fadhil 1993: 252–253, no. 9 = ND 684: 6–7 and r. 6'–9'). Issār-šumu-iqīša, the chief architect (^{luz}GAL' *še-la-pa-a-a*) from Assur in the reign of Tiglath-pileser III (742? BCE) appears in a most remarkable list of witnesses on a document for the acquisition of a field by Bābu-šumu-iddina, who was probably some cult official (*zabardabbu*) of Aššur and the ancestor of an important family of scribes and exorcists, the owners of the N4 archive and library (May 2018). Of fourteen witnesses in this list, nine are priests and scholars in high positions: a scribe of the god, a priest of the god (apparently Aššur), a priest of Nabû, the chief *kurgarru*, three physicians, a scribe, and the aforementioned chief architect, who is the third in the list after the scribe and the priest of the god (Deller et al. 1995: 127, no. 136 = VAT 9749 r. 10–e. 1, especially r. 12). The purchase deed itself was found in the N 24 archive (N 24 [11]), also called the archive of the architects (Donbaz/Parpola 2001: 71; Pedersén 1986: 116). Urnī, the chief architect and Ḥaḥā, an architect from Imgur-Il-lil appear in the list of witnesses together with two priests and a scribe on a sale deed for a field (BT 106 r. 4–13; 734 BCE). The chief architect is the first in the list. An architect Abi-ul-idi from Assur acts as a witness among members of the staff of the temple of Ištar (A 3201 r. 8; 732 BCE). Note also the tablet for the purchase of a slave by Qurdi-Gula, an architect (^{luz}se-

Top-ranking builders, whom I here call architects, were associated with wisdom. Enki, the god of wisdom, stands at the side of the god of construction Mušda(ma);²² and Mušda (^dŠITIM) is equated with ^dEa ša itinni in one of the Ninive copies of An = Anum, an explanatory list of gods.²³ Both Kulla and Mušda(ma) were known as the *itinnu* and *šitimgallu* of Ea in building rituals and incantations.²⁴ In one building ritual

lap-pa-a-a) from Assur, where five priests of various deities are followed by the chief architect (^{luz}GAL' *še-la-pa-a-a*) in the list of witnesses (Deller et al. 1995: 116–117, no. 127 = VAT 8915: 8–9, r. 30–35, 636* BCE). This tablet also comes from the N 24 archive of “architects” (Pedersén 1986: 116, see above), of which Qurdi-Gula is the central figure. See also SAA 7, 154 (fn. 13 above).

For NB and LB see fns. 17 and 18 above.

22 In Enki and the World Order II. 341–348 (esp. 347) it is Enki who makes Mušdama responsible for the entire construction process. Mušdama is called *šidim-gal* of Enlil (<http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/etcsl.cgi?text=c.1.1.3&display=Crit&char-enc=gcirc#>, last accessed 11.08.2016). In the inscriptions of Sargon II (Fuchs 1994: 41, Zyl 60) Mušda(ma) (^dŠITIM) is an architect of Ea (*šitim-gal-lum*). The god of construction (as well as the brick god) is referred to as an architect of the chief god and reflects the relationship of the most prominent of the earthly architects to their earthly rulers (see also fns. 24 and 76).

23 ^mMuš-da ^dšidim : ^dEa ša i-tin-ni CT 25 48, 9 (= K. 4366 9).

24 For Kulla, see Ambos 2004: 134–135, II. A.3.6, c+4'. In the incantation to Mušda(ma), II.B.2 = K. 4167, Mušda(ma) is called

Fig. 3: Stele of Nebuchadnezzar II depicting him as an “architect” of Entemenanki holding the “broken reed” measuring rode(?). The plan and the elevation of the ziqqurat appear beside the king at the left (after CUSAS 17: pl. 64, no. 76. Reproduced with kind permission of David Owen).

in a broken context the following terms are all mentioned together:²⁵ the house of craftsmen or scholars (*bīt ummāni*), plans (*uṣurāte*, GIŠ.ĤUR^{mes}), the wisdom of Ea (*nemēqi* ^dEa), experts (*mudû*), and architects (*itinnû*, ^{lu2}ŠITIM^{mes}).²⁶ Sennacherib claims his “palace without a rival” was built by the skill of “wise architects,” (*šitimgallu enqûte*).²⁷ In Mesopotamia an architect’s skill was tantamount to “wisdom.”

One of the skills of an architect was drafting. The earliest architectural drawings, i.e. plans combined with elevations or simple ground plans, come from the Old Akkadian period.²⁸ The most famous is Gudea’s plan of Eninnu. Gudea’s statues B and F represent him as an architect, holding a tablet, a stylus and a ruler. On the tablet of Statue B is an architectural plan combined with elevation of an enclosure with six gates.²⁹ Combining

a ground plan with an elevation in the same drawing was the Mesopotamian way of representing a three-dimensional structure in a two-dimensional media.³⁰ The idea of representing the architectural and geographical environment by combining a plan and an elevation persisted and is found on Neo-Assyrian reliefs as well (fig. 2). In the Neo-Babylonian period we already find an elevation drawn separately beside a plan, as is done in modern drafts (fig. 3).³¹ By and large most house ground plans do not differ much from modern ones but, even when dimensions are indicated, Mesopotamian plans were not drawn to scale.³² A Neo-Bab-

ŠITIM.GAL of Enlil, but acts on orders of Ea (Ambos 2004: 148–149; II.B.2 (= K. 4167), 19–21 and 17–18 respectively).

25 Ambos 2004: 118–119, II.A.2 (= K. 48+), 6–8 and 12.

26 Unfortunately, both the word modified by *mudû* and the modifier of *itinnû* are lost, but it is clear that two parallel synonymous expressions for expert builders were used.

27 RINAP 3/1, 22 vi 57. *Enqûte* is an epithet often applied to *ummāne* and *tuṣšārru*; see CAD E 151–152 s.v. *emqu* a.

28 Dolce 2000: 373–375, figs. 1–4; Baggs 2011: 568–570 and 578–579, nos. 1–8.

29 That of Statue F is blank; see Suter 2000: 58, RIME 3/1: 30, 46;

Johansen 1978: 10–11 with pls. 19–22 (AO 2 = Statue B) and pls. 28–32 (AO 3 = Statue F). According to Johansen’s description, the unit of measurement on the ruler of Statue B equals 1,6 cm (idem: 10, pl. 22); for Statue F it is 1,6–1,7 cm; the full length of the ruler is 27 cm, of which 24,9 cm has unit indications (idem: 10, pl. 32).

30 The same feature is characteristic of the earliest topographical field plans, like the Sargonic map from Gasur. See Robson 1999, fig. 3.4. For the survey of LB field plans, see Nemet-Nejat 1982.

31 For another example of a ziqqurat elevation, see BM 38217 (Wiseman 1972: 141, 143 with figs. 1 and 2). Note that this tablet also has a colophon, which again links architectural drafts to the scholarly tradition.

32 See Heinrich/Seidl 1967, Dolce 2000, and Baggs 2011 for the overview of Mesopotamian ground plans and, e.g., VAT 7031 = Schneider 1930: pl. 126, no. 504 = Robson 1999: 148, fig. 9.6;

ylonian ground plan of a temple from Sippar seems to outline the bricks,³³ while the dimensions of bricks were standard and related to the area units. Clearly in the Neo-Babylonian period an approach to architectural drafting close to modern was being formulated.

Donald Wiseman provides convincing evidence to show that drawing plans of buildings and fields was a part of a Mesopotamian scribe's mathematical training.³⁴ Very many cuneiform mathematical texts deal with construction.³⁵ There are sets of problems dealing with bricks exclusively, such as the 60 problems in YBC 4608,³⁶ and those in YBC 4607 and so forth. The coefficients lists BM 36776 and U17213b (= UET 5, 859) contain only brick coefficients.³⁷ The set of mathematical problems upon a rectangular prism from Larsa, AO 8862 includes two subsequent architectural problems. In definitions of them both an architect (*itinnu*) demands of a mathematician to compute how many bricks workers from a building gang need to carry over a certain distance and to calculate the grain ration needed for them in proportion to their work-load. Both problems explore proportions.³⁸ The ¹⁰²ŠITIM figures also as a protagonist in Problem 3 in YBC 4673.³⁹ It is a text dealing exclusively with construction problems, mostly for houses but also for dams. The architect and the mathematician have been required to work closely together. Mathematical problems may well have been composed for an architect as the person in overall charge of construction.

Naturally, the question arises if we have cuneiform texts associated with architects which deal with more than brickwork. I turn first to YBC 5022, a list of coefficients presumably also from Larsa.⁴⁰ I will argue that it can be called a "Manual of an Architect." Its caption, IGI.GUB.BA *ša ne₂-pe-eš₂₀-tum*, at first sight appears to be ungrammatical, and an error for *ša nēpeštīm*. But since the text has an apparent nominative for an expected genitive case in three more lines,⁴¹ we have to explain

ša ne₂-pe-eš₂₀-tum as genitive.⁴² Even so, the word *nēpeštum* needs further commentary. Unlike *nēpešum* "procedure, mathematical operation,"⁴³ which is common in mathematical texts, *nēpeštum* is not attested in the context of calculations except here in YBC 5022. Cuneiform mathematicians give the same meaning to *nēpeštum* in YBC 5022 as is given to *nēpešum* elsewhere. Otto Neugebauer and Abraham Sachs transliterate IGI.GUB.BA-*ša ne₂-pe-eš₂₀-tum* and translate "the thing in connection with which the operation is to be performed," or in plain words "of the operation, its coefficient."⁴⁴ Eleanor Robson, taking *epēšum* to mean "to calculate, to perform a calculation," interprets *nēpeštum* as "method of calculation," and translates "coefficients for calculation(?)"⁴⁵ Closer to the truth in my opinion is Wolfram von Soden's suggested translation "Aufstellung," meaning an estimation of costs,⁴⁶ although his translation reflects the content and purpose of the list as a whole rather than the meaning of *nēpeštum* in it. The verb *epēšum* in building inscriptions and rituals etc. usually means "to construct" and occurs more often than *banû*, so *nēpeštum* could mean "workmanship, construction."⁴⁷ From this we may deduce that in YBC 5022 the word means simply "construction," and the caption for this list means "coefficient for construction."

The content of the list confirms this suggestion. According to Robson's general classification of the kinds of coefficients, YBC 5022 includes coefficients of quantity surveying, storage, metals, geometrical coefficients, and some others, as other Old Babylonian coefficient lists do.⁴⁸ A close look into the particular coefficients listed can help us to establish what for these were the ones selected.⁴⁹

Donald 1962: 184 = Robson 1999: 150, fig. 9.7, and de Genouillac 1925, pl. 39 (D.30.R, D.30.F) = Robson 1999: 150, fig. 9.8.

33 See Baggs 2011: 577, no. 32; 585–586 with figs. 32–32b. Note that on the back of this tablet the staircase is indicated within the draft (*ibid.*, fig. 32b).

34 Wiseman 1972: 145.

35 MCT: 91–99, YBC 4067 is a set of problems only related to bricks (OB); YBC 7284 has a coefficient of transformation for the volume of bricks to the units of weight (OB); YBC 10722 includes a problem on brick transportation (OB); in YBC 7997 the brick kiln capacity problem (OB) contains a very high percentage of Sumerograms, and YBC 4067 consists almost only of Sumerograms. See also Nemet-Nejat 1993: 27–35 and Friberg 1996 for the full survey and discussion of the problem texts dealing with bricks and brickwork.

36 MKT 1: 389–402.

37 Robson's lists L and M respectively. The former is LB and the latter is OB (see Robson 1999: esp. 206–207); she notes that the entirely logographic list M "appears to be a short extract from a longer list" (*ibid.* 24).

38 MKT 1: 111–112, iii 32–iv 6 and iv 7–26; both problems are provided with solutions.

39 MKT 3: 29.

40 This text exhibits the same orthographic style of *Pleneschreibung* as the aforementioned AO 8862.

41 Ll. 56b, 59, and 65.

42 TUM can also have a reading *tim₂* in OB, but it is uncertain; see Borger 2010: 319, no. 354 TUM. For the instances of genitive interchanging with nominative in the genitive construction in OB, see, e.g., CAD S 252–253 s.v. *sikkatu* B in *rabi sikkati*.

43 See, e.g., CAD N/2 168 s.v. *nēpešum* 1b, though the CAD collection of usages of *nēpešum* in mathematical texts is rather poor. Note *nēpešum* can also mean "construction."

44 MCT: 132 with n. 298 and apud Robson 1999: 21, n. 14; Vaiman 1961: 37 "их иги-губ-ба операции" ("their IGI.GUB.BA of operation") obviously followed Neugebauer and Sachs.

45 Robson 1999: 21.

46 AHW 778, s.v. *nēpeštum* 6.

47 This is, however correct for the NA period. See CAD N/2 167 s.v. *nēpeštum* 3. For *nēpeštum* as "construction", see RINAP 3/1, 22 vi 54 in the context of ll. 51–58 regarding *šitimgallu enqūte*, and VAB 4, p. 76, iii 14 = Nebuchadnezzar, 1 as *ne₂-pel-ta'-ša'*, collated by P.-R. Berger, apud AHW 778b s.v. *nēpeštum* 5 and CAD N/2 167 s.v. *nēpeštum* 3. In OB *nēpeštum* is commonly attested in conjunction with extispicy (CAD. s.v. *nēpeštum* 1).

48 Robson 1999: 22, table 6. The percentage of quantity surveying coefficients in this list (43%) is one of the largest among the Old Babylonian coefficient lists.

49 In Robson's opinion, this list was compiled from several different lists (Robson 1999: 22).

YBC 5022:⁵⁰

1	IGI.GUB.BA <i>ša ne₂-pe-eš₂₀-tum</i>	Coefficient for construction/workmanship
	4.30 <i>na-az-ba-al</i> SIG ₄	4,30,0, the carriage of bricks
	7.12 <i>na-al-ba-an-ša</i>	7;12, its brickage
	5.24 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> SIG ₄ .AB ₂	5;24, the brickage of a half brick
5	3.22.30 <i>na-az-ba-al-ša</i>	3,22,30, its carriage
	2.42 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> SIG ₄ .AL.UR ₃ .RA	2;42, the brickage of a baked brick
	1.41.15 <i>na-az-ba-al-ša</i>	1,41,15, its carriage
	1.40 <i>na-az-ba-al</i> SAḪAR	1;40, the carriage of earth
	1.12 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> 1 KUŠ ₃ SIG ₄	1;12, the brickage of a 1-cubit brick
10	45 <i>na-az-ba-al-ša</i>	45,0, its carriage
	4.48 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> ½ KUŠ ₃ SIG ₄	4;48, the brickage of a ½-cubit brick
	4.23.36 <i>na-az-ba-al-ša</i>	4,23,36, ⁵¹ its carriage
	9 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> ⅓ KUŠ ₃ SIG ₄	9, the brickage of a ⅓-cubit brick
	8.20 <i>na-al-ba-an</i> IM.DUGUD	8;20, the brickage of clay lumps
15	7.38 <i>na-az-ba-al-ša</i>	7,38,0, its carriage
	7.12 <i>ša</i> SIG ₄ .ANŠE	7;12, of a (regular) brick stack (of standard dimensions)
	3.45 <i>ša</i> IM.DU ₃ .A	0;3,45 of an earth wall
	15 <i>ša</i> ESIR ₂ .ḪA ₅ .RA ₂ .A	0;15, of dried bitumen ⁵²
	30 <i>ša</i> SAG.DU ₃	0;30, of a triangle
20	‘5?’ <i>ša</i> GAN ₂ GUR ₂	0;5, of the area of a circle
	‘15 u ₃ 10’ <i>ša</i> GAN ₂ U ₄ .SAKAR	0;15 and 0;10, of the area of a “crescent”
	1.12 <i>ra-tu₃-um</i> <i>ša</i> URUDU	1,12, a mold (tube) ⁵³ of copper
	1.30 <i>ra-tu₃-um</i> <i>ša</i> KU ₃ .BABBAR	1,30, a mold (tube) of silver
	1.48 <i>ra-tu₃-um</i> <i>ša</i> KU ₃ .GI	1,48, a mold (tube) of gold
25	2.15 <i>ru-uq-qum</i> <i>ša</i> KU ₃ .GI	2,15, a sheet of gold
	4 <i>ru-uq-qum</i> <i>ša</i> KU ₃ .BABBAR	4,0, a sheet of silver
	2.24 <i>ru-uq-qum</i> <i>ša</i> AN.NA	2,24, a sheet of tin
	2.8 <i>ru-uq-qum</i> <i>ša</i> SU ₃ .AG ₂	2,8, a sheet of SU ₃ .AG ₂ -metal ⁵⁴
	6 <i>ša</i> ⁵⁵ MA ₂ .LA ₂	6,0,0, of a cargo-boat.
30	6.40 <i>ša</i> E ₂ .KIŠIB ŠE	6,40,0, of grain storage
	3.36 <i>ša</i> E ₂ .KIŠIB IN.NU.DA	0;3,36, the storage of straw
	3.45 <i>ša</i> E ₂ .KIŠIB SUḪ ₄	0;3,45, of the storage of <i>matting</i>
	15 <i>ša</i> E ₂ .KIŠIB A	15, of the storage of water

Reverse

	3.20 <i>ša</i> SIG ₄ .AL.UR ₃ .RA	3;20, of baked brick
35	1.52.30 <i>ša</i> SIG ₄ .AL.UR ₃ .RA KI.2	1;52,30, of baked brick (second)
	<1>4.24 <i>ma-aš-qa₂-al-tum</i> <i>ša</i> SIG ₄	<1>4,24,0, weight of a brick
	<<1>>.12 <i>ša</i> ḫa-al-lu-u ₂ -um	<<1>>12, of the ḫallûm ⁵⁵
	14.24 <i>ta-ad-di-tum</i> <i>ša</i> SIG ₄	14,24, a layer of bricks
	45 <i>mu-ut-ta-al-li-ik-tum</i>	45,0, going
40	18 <i>i-im-lu-u₂-um</i>	18, <i>imlûm</i> ⁵⁶
	6 <i>ma-aš-šû-u₂-um</i> [ša] ‘SIG ₄ ’	6, basket [of] ‘bricks’
	1.40 <i>ma-aš-šû-u₂-um</i> <i>ša</i> SAḪAR	1;40, basket of earth
	10 GIN ₂ EŠ ₂ .GAR ₃ LU ₂ .1	10 shekels, work-load of 1 man
	1.20 u ₃ ‘15’ <i>na-az-ba-al</i> A	1;20 and 15, carriage of water

50 The transliteration follows Robson 1999: 202–204. The translation deviates from hers mostly in cases discussed above and below.

51 According to Robson 1999: 85 this is an error. The coefficient should have been 3,0,0.

52 See the discussion in CAD I 311b–312a (s.v. *ittû*) regarding different kinds of bitumen and the various Sumerian terms for it.

53 *Rāṭum* originally meant “channel” including birth canal, strongly connoting a channel “into which something is poured” (CAD R 219–220 s.v. *rāṭum*). In that sense it was used for a metal-casting mold (ibid. 220, s.v. *rāṭum* d). Probably these were tubular molds for ingots of standard dimensions.

54 See Robson 1999: 128, who quotes bibliography for reading SU₃.AG₂ as *elmēšum*, an unidentified precious stone or metal.

55 Robson 1999: 62 reads <<1>>12,0,0 *ša-ḫa-al-lu-u₂-um*. *šahallûm* is a rare word which she left untranslated (cf. CAD Š/1 77a “a milling product”?). The initial *ša* might represent the indirect genitive, resulting in “of the ḫallûm, perhaps some kind of vessel” (CAD Ḫ 45b s.v. *ḫallu* B). For the coefficient emendation here, see Robson 1999: 63 with n. 6.

56 For the detailed discussion, see Robson 1999: 131–133, who also refrains from translating the word.

45	2.13 ʾ20 u ₃ 1:15	ša ^{giš} <<tup>>DUSU	0;0,2,13, 20 and 1,15, of a basket
	ʾ3:[22].ʾ30	ša IM	ʾ3:[22],ʾ30, of clay
	[13].ʾ20	ša GAN ₂ MA ₂ .GUR ₈	0;13,20, of the area of a barge
	ʾ53.20	ša GAN ₂ ZA ₃ .MI ₂	0;53,20, of the area of a lyre
	ʾ5ʾ2.30 u ₃ 12.30	ša GAN ₂ ʾPAN	0;52,30 and 0;12,30, of the area of a bow
50	26.40	ša GEŠTU ZA ₃ .MI ₂	0;26,40, a concave square
	3.30	ša GAN ₂ ʾPAN KI.2	3;30, of the area of a bow, second
	4.20	ša GAN ₂ U ₄ .SAKAR KI.2	4 (and) 0;20, of the area of a “crescent,” second
	4.36 10	ša GAN ₂ GUR ₂ KI.2	4,36 (and) 0;10, of the area of a circle, second
	45	ša GAN ₂ U ₄ .SAKAR KI.3	0;45, of the area of a “crescent,” third
55	ʾ20.48 6	ša GIR ₄ AD.KID	20, 48 (and) 6, of the reed-worker’s oven for melting of bitumen) ⁵⁷
56a, b	ʾ3ʾ6	IM.BABBAR	ʾ3ʾ6, gypsum;
	54	ša ka-lu-u ₂ -um	54, of orpiment
57a, b	ʾ20ʾ	ša ESIR ₂ ʾ	ʾ20ʾ, of bitumen?;
	20	ša ^{na} ₄ KUR.RA	20, of alum
	ʾ4.48	ša ku-bu-ur-re-e GIŠ	4,48,0, of the thickness of a log
	40	ša DU ₃ ^{giš} šu-rum ⁵⁸	0;40, of building reeds (for dams)
60	12	ma-al-ta-ak-kum ša mu-ši-im	0;12, the water-clock of the night
	4.48	ša E ₂ .KIŠIB ŠE	4,48,0, storage of grain
	24	PI-lu-u ₂ -tum ša GI [(x)]	24, ... of reed [...?]
63a, b	1	ši ₂ -li-ip-tum	1, a diagonal/rectangle; ⁵⁹
	1	zi-it-tum	1, a share;
	1	GI ḤAŠ.A	1, a broken reed
65	57.36	ša eb-lu-u ₂ -um	0;57,36, of a rope
		^d Nisaba	Nisaba

57 See Robson 1999: 135 for the explanation why three separate coefficients should be read here. MCT: 135 “of the wicker-worker’s (asphalt) oven;” ETCSL translates ad-KID as “basket weaver” (<http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/edition2/etcslemma.php>, last access 28.07.2016) and PSD as “basket weaver, reed worker” in <http://psd.museum.upenn.edu/epsd/nepsd-frame.html> (last access 28.07.2016) and as “reed worker” in PSD A/3 20–23, s.v. ad-KID. For gir₄ ad-KID, see CAD A/2 495a, s.v. *atkuppu* (lexical section).

58 Attested only here.

59 Robson 1999: 45 translates “rectangle” here. Vaiman 1961: 38, 50 uses the term “diagonal” when discussing this line. Both translations can be correct for *šilipum* (CDA 338a), since a diagonal can stand *pars pro toto* for a rectangle; Vaiman 1961: 50 saw it as the diagonal of a rhombus, a different kind of parallelogram.

Fig. 4: Coefficients' kinds in YBC 5022.

Of 76⁶⁰ coefficients of this almost intact list, 47 items (about 62%) are actual construction materials (bricks, earth, reeds, clay,⁶¹ logs, water, straw) or concern transporting or storing them (fig. 4).⁶² Most (about a quarter) of the coefficients are for bricks as building material.

60 Two numerical values of coefficients with the same title (ll. 21, 44, 49, 52, and 53) are counted as separate coefficients that might have had served different needs in computations. Lines 45 and 55 each apparently contain three coefficients with the same name.

61 A clay coefficient (l. 46) is attested only in this list (Robson 1999: 137).

62 Only three coefficients in this list are not adequately understood (ll. 32, 37, 40). The coefficient for matting storage seems also to be the coefficient of construction. The meaning of *hallûm* and *imlûm* is unknown, but since they appear among coefficients related to brickwork and earthwork they are probably also some type of basic construction material.

All types of brick are mentioned except the $\frac{2}{3}$ brick; the mention of a coefficient for a $\frac{1}{3}$ brick (l. 13) is unique to this list. Of five storage coefficients three deal with building materials: ll. 31–33, water, matting(?), and straw. Thus, in concern of the building materials, their storage and carriage, this list is the most detailed of all Old Babylonian lists of coefficients. The coefficients for work-load in line 43, for the cargo-boat to transport bricks in line 29⁶³ and the three(?) for the reed-workers' bitumen oven in line 55 all relate to construction. The daily distance construction workers covered in transporting building materials is referred to as “go-

63 In conjunction with the cargo-boat used for transporting various types of bricks, see Robson 1999: 113 (BM 85194).

ing” (l. 39).⁶⁴ YBC 5022 includes two grain storage coefficients (ll. 30 and 61) and grain rations for workers were the responsibility of an architect, as we saw earlier in problems in AO 8862. The coefficients at the end of the list (ll. 56–59) relate to the finer building materials than bricks, including bitumen, bundles of reeds,⁶⁵ and wood logs; gypsum, ochre⁶⁶, and alum were used for plaster, paint and dye.

Lines 22–28 form a group of seven coefficients of metals, three of molds (*rāṭum*) and four of sheets (*ruqqum*). The Mesopotamian architect was naturally responsible for the design of a building. He needed coefficients of sheet metal to calculate amounts for plating statues,⁶⁷ doors⁶⁸ and temple cella walls.⁶⁹ Metal architectural details, for which *rāṭum* coefficients would have been needed, can be seen in the famous Early Dynastic copper lintel of the Tall al-‘Ubaid temple.⁷⁰ The correspondence of Sargon⁷¹ and the inscriptions of Sennacherib⁷² describe the luxurious metal work that adorned the palaces of Dūr Šarrukīn and Ninive, where bronze and cooper bulls and lion colossi and sphinxes served as column bases (fig. 5).⁷³ The Gudea Statue B inscription lists gold among the other building materials⁷⁴ and mentions silver, cooper, tin, and bronze for the production of statues.⁷⁵ Finally, from the ritual of the investiture of the divine statue we see that an architect used metals for a statue.⁷⁶

Regarding the geometrical coefficients, Vaiman wrote in conclusion to his article “Interpretation of the Geometrical Constants in the Cuneiform List TMS I from Susa:”

Unfortunately, so far we cannot say for certain the purpose of the Babylonians for computing various

kinds of geometrical constants... . Some if not all the geometrical constants may have been used in computations connected with craftsmanship and construction. This doubtless applies to the coefficients of area and the diameter and radius of a circle.”⁷⁷

The selection of mathematical coefficients⁷⁸ in YBC 5022 is indeed remarkable. There are coefficients of most basic geometrical forms and of more sophisticated ones used in ornaments. The coefficients of the latter are restricted, in fact, to the cuneiform mathematics. There are three groups of mathematical coefficients in this text: lines 19–21; 47–54; in line 63 the coefficients of a share and of a diagonal of a rectangle appear. The first group includes coefficients of a triangle, a circle and a “crescent.”⁷⁹ Two more coefficients of a “crescent” appear in the second group. The importance of such basic shapes as the triangle, rectangle, and circle and its parts for architecture is obvious. Computation for triangles, circles and parts of a circle were necessary for general architectural features in a building and also for decorations and ornaments.⁸⁰

In relation to ornaments, BM 15285 should be discussed.⁸¹ Anne Kilmer in her pioneering research on the design names in Akkadian and Sumerian referred to this outstanding document.⁸² Here I refrain from discussing the obviously ornamental character of the geometric figures represented by the diagrams supplied for each problem in this text, on which Kilmer and Jöran Friberg concentrated,⁸³ but investigate the purpose of composing this set of problems. The tablet contains 40 problem definitions, all starting with “The side of a square is 1 UŠ.” Then follows a description of a figure or set of figures indented into the square. The question in every problem is “What is its or their area?”

64 For parallels and discussion, see Robson 1999: 78–82.

65 Not necessarily for dams, see CAD Š/3 369 s.v. *širu* A c; cf. Robson 1999: 102–106.

66 *Kalū* is most probably ochre; it was used as a coating material together with gypsum, and on its own especially for writing boards; see CAD K 94, s.v. *kalū* c and d.

67 E.g., Zettler/Horne 1998: 51, no.1; 52, no. 2; 53: no. 3; 58, no. 4; and one of two famous table legs in a form of a ram (ibid.: opposite p. 43).

68 For instance, the bronze bands of the Balawat Gates of Assurnasirpal II and Shalmaneser III (King 1915, Schachner 2007).

69 RINAP 4, 1 v 38–39 (Esarhaddon); for bronze and tin bands plating columns and silver and gold inlays on statues see RINAP 3/1, 17 vii 20–40 (Sennacherib). For metalworking techniques and the archaeological evidence, see Aruz 2003: 79–88 and passim; for the third millennium Mesopotamia, see Millerman 2008: 7–9 with fig. 8 on Ur cemetery; on Late Assyrian metalwork, see Curtis 2013.

70 E.g., Aruz 2003: 85, fig. 30.

71 SAA 1, 66.

72 RINAP 3/1, 1: 83; 17, iv 89–vii 40.

73 Incredulously, Sennacherib boasts that he was the first king to decorate his palace with bronze and copper bulls and lion colossi, columns and sphinxes serving as column bases; in fact a letter from his father’s treasurer to Sargon (SAA 1, 66) states that similar luxurious bronze work adorned Dūr Šarrukīn.

74 RIME 3/1 Gudea E3/1.1.7.StB vi 33–42.

75 RIME 3/1 Gudea E3/1.1.7.StB vii 49–53.

76 A god (name broken, most probably Mušda(ma) or Kulla) mentioned in connection (the context is badly broken) with gold and silver has the epithet ŠITIM.GAL of Anu; see Ambos 2004: 152–153, II.C.1a (= K. 3472), 7.

77 Vaiman 1963: 86: “К сожалению мы ничего достоверного не можем сказать о цели, которую преследовали вавилоняне, вычисляя различного рода геометрические постоянные Если и не все, то по крайней мере некоторые геометрические постоянные могли использоваться в расчетах, связанных с ремесленным производством и строительной деятельностью (в отношении постоянных площади, диаметра и радиуса круга это несомненно).”

78 The definition of mathematical coefficients here follows Vaiman 1961: 50–51 and includes geometrical coefficients and coefficients of share (proportion) as opposed to the much more numerous group, which he called “empirical constants” (ibid.: 38–50).

79 Friberg 1987–1990: 555 and Robson (e.g., 2000: 38–39) translate “semicircle.” However, neither explains the constants 0;20 and 0;45 of YBC 5022: 52, 54. Rechecking may show that these constants could relate to other kinds of segments.

80 On baked-brick circles semicircles, sectors, and segments used in column construction, as attested from Gudea (at Ġirsu) through the Neo-Assyrian period (at Tall ar-Rimāh); see Robson 1999: 142–145 and Oates 1990, especially 392–395 with pls. 1–2 and fig. 4. For these and even more sophisticated brick shapes, see Kara-indaš’s temple of Inana at Uruk (Jakob-Rost et al. 1990: 95, no. 42).

81 E.g., Robson 1999: 208–217 including a handcopy and references to previous editions.

82 Kilmer 1990: 85–90.

83 Friberg 2007: 164–170. J. Friberg, however, discusses Mesopotamian artistic compositions as based on geometrical figures, while A. Kilmer investigates the ornaments themselves, their origin, and Sumerian and Akkadian terms for them.

Fig. 5: Column bases in form of lamassu and lions in Sennacherib’s South-West Palace as depicted on the reliefs of the Room H of the North Palace of Assurbanipal. According to RINAP 3/1, 1: 83; 17, iv 89–vii 40 they were made of bronze and cooper (after Barnett 1976: pl. 23. © Trustees of the British Museum).

To clarify the definition, each problem is illustrated with a neat drawing. The only purpose in solving these problems would be to compute the amount of material for ornamenting walls and floors. Ornamental wall coatings involved indented geometrical figures in Mesopotamia from the earliest period.⁸⁴ By knowing the amounts necessary for one square UŠ of a surface, an architect could easily compute what was needed for an entire surface. It is, of course, tempting to claim, that the gigantic rectangle of one square UŠ⁸⁵ suggests that these problems were applied to monumental architecture. However, when converted into other measures,⁸⁶ the same problem solutions can be applied to smaller areas. The principle of similarity of figures was intuitively used in problem solutions.⁸⁷ By scaling computations for areas from a base of one square UŠ for any ornament amounts for surfaces of any dimension can be calculated. Solving these problems gave an architect the material needed for 40 types of ornament. The exotic forms of some of the figures cannot have been of pure geometrical interest and so favour the suggestion that this problem had a practical purpose in computing the area of any ornament. The last problem in BM 15285 discusses areas of concave triangles and squares and of “barges.” The coefficients of two of these ornaments, the concave square and the “barge,” are also given in the list YBC 5022, there together with two coefficients of an area of a bow and an obscure $GAN_2 ZA_3.MI_2$.⁸⁸ The ornaments of concave triangle and concave square (*apsamikku*) paired with the “barge” occur in Mesopotamia

84 See, e.g., Aruz 2003: 18–19, no. 5 and fig. 4 for the clay-cone wall mosaics from the forth millennium Uruk and pp. 85–86, nos. 44a, b for shell-inlayed columns from early Dynastic (III) Tall al-Ubaid.

85 Ca. 360 × 360 m.

86 On the conversion of various units, see Vaiman 1961: 32–34.

87 See, e.g., Vaiman 1961: 110, 126.

88 Robson 1999: 57 suggests that it is $GI_5.GAN_2 ZA_3.MI_2$ of BM 15285.

from the earliest times through to the first millennium⁸⁹ and probably came from Harrapa.⁹⁰

To sum up, of 76 coefficients of YBC 5022⁹¹ only two are not directly connected with the duties of an architect. These are the coefficient of share⁹² and the coefficient of a water-clock of the night in line 60. But the latter would be of general use in any construction process.⁹³ Apart from two lists of coefficients,⁹⁴ the term “share” is found only in conjunction with the division of property.⁹⁵ The problems involving “share” are progression problems similar to those that an architect was to deal with.⁹⁶ The list ends with the coefficients of a broken reed and a rope, the main tools of the Mesopotamian architect, to be used like a ruler and tape-measure. The “broken reed” might have functioned like a folding ruler. It might be a kind of telescopic measuring rod like the one that Nebuchadnezzar II holds on a stele, where he is represented as an “architect” of Etemenanki (fig. 3).⁹⁷

89 For *apsamikku*-ornaments in the earliest period (Halaf), see Kilmer 1990: 87, fig. 6. For concave triangles and squares as well as “barges” in Assyrian architectural surface decorations, see Albenda 1978, especially fig. 3 and pls. 19–22 and Albenda 2005: 16, pls. 3–4; 25, pl. 4a; 35, pl. 9; 37, pl. 11; 40, pl. 13; 44, pl. 17; 46, pl. 18. Assyrian glazed wall plaques were also shaped as concave squares and were very common in Neo-Assyrian palatial décor (e.g., Curtis/Reade 1995: 103, no. 51). See also the note of P. Albenda on Neo-Assyrian geometrical designs in conjunction with BM 15285 (Albenda 2017).

90 Regarding the Harrapan origin of the *apsamikku*-ornament, see Kilmer 1990: 87 with figs. 6–7 and also Erlenmeyer/Erlenmeyer 1966: 25, figs. 15–16. For *apsamikku* in mathematical texts, see Vaiman 1959 and Robson 2007.

91 Three(?) are unidentified; see fn. 62.

92 *Zittum*, l. 69.

93 Robson (1999: 129–130) relates this coefficient to the astronomical constants based on its use in the NB observations of the moon. There is, however, no evidence for observations of the moon in the OB period.

94 YBC 5022 and A 3553.

95 Inheritance, income, booty, property, payment or delivery; see CAD Z 139–147 s.v. *zittu* 1–4.

96 AO 8862. For the discussion of the progression problems, see Muroi 1988 and most recently Melville 2005.

97 An Old Babylonian copper(?) cubit was excavated at Nippur (*Nippurelle*, Unger 1916: pl. 1). Note that this stele of Nebuchadnezzar II continues the tradition of stele monuments

Building construction was the most developed and important of early Mesopotamian technologies. The overwhelming majority of the early cuneiform mathematical texts relates to building techniques. A great number of early cuneiform mathematical texts in general and OB texts in particular, including problems and coefficient lists, deal with bricks and other building materials. Vaiman pointed to the “importance of the ‘applied’ mathematics” of the Sumerians⁹⁸ for the development of the theoretical mathematics in the OB period.⁹⁹ Since the Ur III period units of volume and area are expressed also as brick units.¹⁰⁰ Computations related to bricks, brickwork, and brick metrology¹⁰¹ resulted in the development of stereometry, which started as calculating the volumes of walls and dams of various shapes.¹⁰² This “brickometry” advanced cuneiform mathematics¹⁰³ as much as the land plots measuring advanced geometry, “measuring the earth.” Many Old Babylonian mathematical texts related to construction are written almost entirely in Sumerograms. Apparently they go back to the Ur III period,¹⁰⁴ but their subject matter originated in the Early Dynastic period if not before.¹⁰⁵

Already in the Early Dynastic period the craft of the master-builder was highly developed, with many branches and a sophisticated hierarchy. The Ur III pe-

riod marked the zenith of monumental construction.¹⁰⁶ To be an architect involved closely connecting with mathematics and with what was considered to be “wisdom.” The prosopography of architects connects them with priests and scribes.¹⁰⁷ Karen Nemet-Nejat lists various kinds of scribes that had diverse specialisations which needed different types of training.¹⁰⁸ An architect needed and must have received advanced mathematical training to become professional. It was suggested by Robson¹⁰⁹ that the Ur III model texts AOT 304 and YBC 9819,¹¹⁰ both dealing with bricks, were used in schools for mathematics tuition. In the OB period schools apparently trained apprentice architects. The brick problem texts YBC 4607, 4608 as well as the list of construction coefficients YBC 5022 seem to have been compiled not only for mathematical education *per se* but also for the mathematical education of architects.¹¹¹ BM 15285 was probably used in teaching computing the areas of decorative ornaments.

The “brickometry,” with its problems and empirical coefficients disappeared, as did its *realia*, but it laid the ground for geometry and stereometry. Not only geometry, but also the designs and decorative techniques of Mesopotamian architecture have persisted in many respects until today¹¹² — *ars longa, vita brevis!*

representing the king as a builder. From the late third millennium, the king is shown on steles, which commemorate his construction projects, receiving measuring tools, a rod and a rope, from a god. This iconographic tradition goes back probably to Ur-Namma (see Suter 2000: 244–251, figs. 33a–34). The measuring rod of Nebuchadnezzar is much more sophisticated; the plan and the elevation of the ziqqurat in front of the king are also an example of the most sophisticated Mesopotamian drafting. The king is represented holding the measuring rod himself, and not as one presented with it by the god. Apparently due to the influence of the iconography of Neo-Assyrian royal steles the king appears as the main protagonist of the depiction, holding a measuring rod like a sceptre. The concept of this stele of Nebuchadnezzar II is the same as that of Statues B and F of Gudea, where the ruler is depicted as an architect with a draft of the temple he had built and a measuring tool.

98 Robson 1999: 2–3 quoting Vaiman 1960 in German; this passage was partly repeated by him in Vaiman 1961: 207 (see above with fn. 3).

99 Vaiman 1961: 207–212.

100 Vaiman 1961: 39–40.

101 Nemet-Nejat 1993: 27–35, Friberg 1996, Robson 1999: 57–110.

102 See also Vaiman 1961: 136–137.

103 See Vaiman 1961: 107 on the terminology for spatial figures as rooted in construction.

104 See Robson’s overview and conclusions (Robson 1999: 138–182).

105 Kilmer 1990: 89–90, Friberg 1978–1979.

106 E.g., the ziqqurat of Ur-Namma (see Jakob-Rost et al. 1990: 25, fig. 12).

107 See fn. 21.

108 Nemet-Nejat 1993: 24–25. Unfortunately, she does not specify the periods for which each scribal profession was attested. Her list includes *šassuku* “field scribe, geometer.” The more precise definition of this profession would be “surveyor.”

109 Robson 1999: 171.

110 Dunham 1982: esp. 28–31.

111 The same was probably the purpose of the OB construction coefficients excerpt U17213b = UET 5, 859.

112 The same geometrical ornaments were widely used for instance in Late Roman *opus sectile* decorations and elsewhere.

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Contents

Preface	xi–xii
Programme	xiii–xxiv
Opening sessions	1–18
Ariane Thomas Hommage à Pierre Amiet Écrit et image dans l'Antiquité orientale	3–10
Nicholas Postgate Bridging the gap – in retrospect and in prospect	11–18
Papers	19–466
Philippe Abrahams et Brigitte Lion Quelques contrats de commandes d'étoffes à Nuzi	21–31
Nikita Artemov Demonization of enemies in Mesopotamian literature A case study in verbal imagery	33–42
Mehmet-Ali Ataç Identifying the big bird in the battle reliefs of Ashurnasirpal II	43–51
Benedetta Bellucci Composite creatures on seal impressions of Nuzi	53–62
Vanessa Bigot Juloux Herméneutique de l'action pour l'étude des relations entre les entités animées et leur <i>agency</i> au Proche-Orient ancien: <i>Hypatia et alii</i>	63–79
Daniel Bodi The divine "image" and "shadow" in iconography, inscriptions and philology	81–91
Daniel Bonneterre La cuisse de Baal Analyse d'un rituel d'intégration	93–101
Sebastian Borkowski "Of marshes, kings, and rebels" On the perception and representation of southern Mesopotamian wetlands at the Neo-Assyrian royal court	103–115
Manuel Ceccarelli Bemerkungen zur vermittelnden Gottheit unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der sumerischen Königshymnen	117–129
Nicolas A. Corfù und Joachim Oelsner Beschriftete Hundestatuetten aus Mesopotamien	131–138
Şevket Dönmez An overview on the excavations at Üçtepe Höyük (ancient Tuşhan) The 1988–1992 excavation seasons	139–146
Lena Fijałkowska "I was swollen with hunger and he kept me alive" The imagery of the legal texts from Emar	147–152

Jeanette C. Fincke The Nuzi apprenticeship contracts	153–161
Gösta Gabriel Decreeing fate and name-giving in <i>enūma eliš</i> Approaching a fundamental Mesopotamian concept with special consideration of the underlying assumptions and of the condition of possibility of human knowledge	163–178
Gérard Gertoux Dating the reigns of Xerxes and Artaxerxes	179–206
Ari Kh. Kamil Une nouvelle archive privée d'un marchand de l'époque d'Ur III	207–223
Fabienne Kilchör und Catherine Mittermayer Text als Bild Graphic Reading am Beispiel der sumerischen Rangstreitgespräche	225–240
John A. Lynch Gilgameš's ghosts A case for Enkidu's <i>Catalog of the Dead</i> as a manual for apprentice exorcists	241–244
Paolo Matthiae Le rapport entre texte et image dans les reliefs de Ḫorsābād Tradition et innovation un siècle et demi après Assurnāṣirpal II	245–254
Natalie N. May Text and architecture: YBC 5022 and BM 15285 as "manuals of an architect"	255–269
Patrick M. Michel Construire l'image, dire les rites Essai sur l'iconographie des rituels hittites	271–279
Robert Middeke-Conlin Estimation and observation A study of two Old Babylonian tabular administrative documents	281–291
Bonka Nedeltscheva The movement of text and image within the layout of an envelope throughout Mesopotamian history	293–300
Paola Negri Scafa 'If the earth quakes...': The Nuzi text SMN 3180	301–308
Herbert Niehr Questions of text and image in ancient Sam'al (Zincirli)	309–319
Aynur Özfırat Dolmens in the Amuq Plain: Kızılkaya survey	321–326
Véronique Pataï Textes et images à Nuzi Le cas du scribe Iṭḫ-apiḫe fils de Taya	327–334
Frances Pinnock Representations of steles in the palace glyptic of Early Syrian Ebla	335–345
Beate Pongratz-Leisten Tigridian royal representation Text and image between tradition and innovation	347–354
Julian Edgeworth Reade Ships bringing timber for the palace of Sargon Alternative presentations of reality	355–368
Melissa Ricetti Identification through image and legend Inscribed seals from Kültepe lower town level II	369–382

Elisa Roßberger Showing off: Old Babylonian “goddess in a structure” plaques revisited	383–398
Nadezda Rudik „Dieser Ziegel ist wie Lapislazuli...“ Ein bisher übersehenes Bauritual im Kontext der frühen sumerischen Beschwörungen	399–409
JoAnn Scurlock <i>Enūma eliš</i> meets the so-called Babylonian Map of the World An image and its text	411–422
Alexander E. Sollee and Johanna Tudeau Step by step: Correcting our mental image of the <i>mušlālu</i>	423–441
Marie-Louise Thomsen Ninĝirsu, Ninurta und Sirius in sumerischem Kontext	443–446
Luděk Vacín All the king's <i>adamindugas</i> Textual images of Ur III sovereigns as managers of the universe	447–457
Aslıhan Yurtsever Beyazit Hittites in North-Central Anatolia A compilation of the current evidence	459–466
Workshop International Relations theory and Ancient Near Eastern history	467–509
Selim F. Adalı and Lucas G. Freire Introduction to the workshop International Relations theory and Ancient Near Eastern history	469–471
Serdar Ş. Güner Balances of power in the Hatti-Egypt-Mittani system (1400–1300 B.C.)	473–479
Lucas G. Freire System and society: The Near East in the second millennium BCE	481–488
Emanuel Pfoh Reconsidering international relations in Southwest Asia during the Late Bronze Age	489–496
Alex Aissaoui A Near Eastern states system before the classical period Comparing the Greek <i>poleis</i> system with ancient Near Eastern state formation	497–504
Selim F. Adalı What is policy impact? Questioning narratives of political events in the last century of the Assyrian Empire	505–509
Extraordinary session Strategies for restoration and reconstruction Museums, heritage sites and archaeological parks in post-war countries	511–515
Cynthia Dunning, Mohamad Fakhro, Denis Genequand, Mirko Novák Strategies for restoration and reconstruction Museums, heritage sites and archaeological parks in post-war countries	513–515
Abbreviations and conventions	517
Indices	517–526